

A STUDY OF GF/PA6 FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES MATERIALS USING PULTRUSION AND DIRECT EXTRUSION METHOD

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I. Introduction

In this study, GF/PA6 fiber reinforced composites with high fiber volume fraction were prepared by pultrusion and direct extrusion. Since pultrusion method obtains a long fiber length, high mechanical properties can be obtained. Direct extrusion can simplify process and improve productivity. Thermal and viscoelastic properties of thermoplastic polymer resin were analyzed to determine optimal conditions for impregnation of resin into reinforcing fibers. Property of composites were confirmed by comparing fiber length. Moreover, We tried to find mechanical properties of final composite material by applying different resins to same glass fiber and checking interfacial bonding strength between polymer resin and fiber.

II. Experimentals

1) Motivation

Fig. 1 (A) Short fiber / Long fiber reinforced composites, (B) Pultrusion, (C) Direct process

2) Purpose

- Establish optimal conditions of GF/PA6 fiber reinforced composites
 - Manufacture of composite materials with high GF content through process control
 - Comparison of physical properties of composite materials using direct and pultrusion
 - Comparison of physical properties of composite materials according to resin type and fiber volume fraction
 - Analysis of composite material properties by interfacial bonding and fiber length analysis

3) Formulation of materials & Manufacturing process

- Formulation of materials
 - Glass fiber : CTG, EDR240 T835
 - PA6 : 1011BRT (Hyosung), GP1100A(W) (LG Chem.)
 - Target fiber weight fraction : 40, 50 wt%
 - Process : Pultrusion, Direct extrusion

Glass fiber	Process	PA6 resin	Fiber weight fraction
EDR240 T835	Pultrusion (P)	1011 BRT (B)	40 wt%
	Direct (D)	GP 110A(W) (G)	50 wt%

Fig. 2 Manufacturing process of Pultrusion (a) and Direct extrusion (b)

III. Results & Discussion

▶ PA6 resin analysis

• DSC, TGA

Fig. 3 PA6 (a) Differential Scanning Calorimetry(DSC), (b) Thermogravimetric analysis(TGA)

- Melting temperature $\approx 220^{\circ}\text{C}$, Process must operate above 220°C for low porosity and high impregnation.
- 5% thermal decomposition temperature $\approx 400^{\circ}\text{C}$, Process should proceed within temperature range that does not degrade physical properties of resin.

• Rotational rheometer

Fig. 4. viscoelastic behavior of PA6 (a) 1011BRT (b) GP1100A(w)

- Machine : Rotational rheometer (TA instrument Ltd., DHR-1)
- Process condition : $230\sim 290^{\circ}\text{C} / 1\text{Hz}$
- Elastic behavior was dramatically increase after 270°C . Excessively high extrusion process temperature are believed to be a difficulty in extruding composites.
- Thorough resin analysis, Optimum process temperature of extruder was determined to 250°C .

▶ Interfacial shear strength

• Single fiber pull out test

▶ Physical properties

• Matrix burn-off method

- Test standard : ASTM D3171-06
- Fiber and resin content calculate using sample weigh
- Sample
 - P = Pultrusion, D = Direct extrusion, B = 1011BRT, G = GP110A(W)
 - Target weight contents = 40, 50wt%
 - Lowest porosity from each sample

Fig. 7 Ashes after burn-off test

Sample	GF content (wt%)	Resin content (wt%)	Density (g/cc)	Fiber volume fraction (%)	Porosity (%)
P-B-40	38.9	61.1	1.419	21.55	2.37
P-B-50	47.4	52.6	1.515	28.06	2.10
P-G-40	40.0	60.0	1.409	21.89	3.03
P-G-50	51.7	48.3	1.581	31.96	1.66
D-B-40	33.8	66.2	1.346	17.77	4.04
D-B-50	47.6	52.4	1.504	27.94	2.87
D-G-40	41.2	58.8	1.429	22.97	2.65
D-G-50	53.1	46.9	1.551	32.16	3.42

▶ Mechanical properties

• Strength and modulus of composites

Fig. 8 Mechanical properties depend on volume fraction of fibers

▶ Fractography

• OM, FE-SEM

Fig. 9 Fiber length & Interfacial bonding Image of Pultrusion and Direct extrusion method

- After Fiber ash was diluted in distilled water, evaporated on glass substrate. Fiber length was observed by OM.
- Pultrusion sample's fiber length is longer than Direct extrusion.
- Fracture surface of tensile test sample was observed by FE-SEM.
- All sample show high mechanical strength.

Conclusions

In this study, Process method, Resin type and Fiber volume fraction were experimented to fabricate GF/PA6 LFT materials with optimum. It was confirmed that mechanical properties of material were superior to pultrusion method rather than direct extrusion method. In addition, The higher the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between resin and fiber, better mechanical properties were obtained. As fiber volume fraction increases, mechanical strength of each sample increases, but increase in elastic modulus increase more than increase in strength. In order to produce fiber-reinforced composites with excellent mechanical strength based on the above experimental results, it is necessary to produce material having a high specific gravity of fiber, long fiber length, high interfacial shear strength and low porosity at the same specific gravity will be necessarily.